

TECHNOLOGY AND THE INTERNET: CONVENIENCE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE**Nurmamatova Shakhzoda Umrbek qizi****SAMDCHTI, Narpay, Faculty of Foreign Languages, Department of Philology and
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Abstract: This article discusses the beneficial aspects of using the Internet for people, as well as the problems that may be encountered. The Internet makes our lives easier and is widely used in education, employment, medicine, daily life, and business. The article also explains how individuals can achieve success by using these opportunities effectively and responsibly.

Keywords: online platforms, websites, video lessons, advertising, online shopping, misinformation, hackers.

Currently, the number of Internet users is increasing day by day. Through the Internet, people's lifestyles become more convenient and efficient. One of the main advantages of the Internet is online shopping, which allows individuals to purchase any product they want. For example, platforms such as Uzum, Pinduoduo, Taobao, OLX.uz, and others provide users with easy access to various goods. Regardless of location, people can buy the items they need at any time. The table below shows statistics on global online shoppers.

The role of the Internet in the field of education is also considered very important. Nowadays, attention to foreign languages has significantly increased. We can learn foreign languages independently through various online platforms. For example, Duolingo, Ibrat Academy, Memrise, Babbel, and others. Through the table below, we can ознако́миться ourselves with the statistics of people learning foreign languages.

European population speaks a foreign language

Eurostat-European population 24.7% speaks 2foreign language

Eurostat-proportion of Europeans 12.3% who speak 3 or more foreign language

Percentage of people aged 18-64 93% in Finland who know a foreign language

The role of the Internet in the field of communication is also considered invaluable. In other words, people have the opportunity to communicate with their distant relatives and loved ones through the Internet by means of video calls and messaging. This strengthens relationships between people and greatly facilitates communication. Platforms such as Skype, Zoom,

Instagram, and Telegram are clear examples of this. The table below shows statistics on the use of global social media platforms.

One of them is the risk of encountering hackers. In other words, when a person creates an account on social media, they enter a large amount of personal information. If this information falls into the hands of hackers, it can cause serious harm. For example, hackers may use personal data to take out loans in someone else's name. As a result, the individual may spend their entire life paying the consequences of such actions.

In addition, excessive dependence on social media negatively affects a person's work and academic performance. For instance, watching unnecessary videos such as Instagram reels wastes a significant amount of time. Similarly, watching TV series continuously on YouTube prevents individuals from allocating time to other productive activities.

In conclusion, it can be stated that if a person has clear goals and a well-defined strategy, they can use the Internet effectively in all areas. Time management plays a crucial role in this process. If an individual organizes their daily schedule properly, decides what to do and when to do it, and follows this plan consistently, they will achieve balanced personal growth. Based on such discipline, a person can reach various achievements in the future.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Source: SellersCommerce and several online e-commerce statistics aggregation websites.
2. Source: Kylian.ai — Bilingualism Statistics.
3. Source: Eurostat — Foreign Language Skills Statistics.
4. Source: Wikipedia — Languages of Finland.
5. DataReportal / We Are Social (2024–2025)
6. Number of global social media users: approximately 5.04–5.41 billion